

THE USE OF ABBREVIATIONS IN DIFFERENT FIELDS

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays abbreviations play an important part in every realm of human endeavor. In this article, I am going to describe the importance of abbreviations in different fields, and some ground rules to apply them in context with some relevant examples.

Key words: abbreviation, definition, medical abbreviations, linguistics, engineering, word-count target, manuscripts.

Once Borisov said, “Abbreviation is not a random phenomenon, it is not a “damage of the language”, a fancy of some people, but an objective regular process stipulated by changes in needs for communication due to development of society and internal patterns of development of the language”. Abbreviation, by definition, is the shortened form of words, terms and phrases, which help to make the writing easy to read and comprehend. Moreover, it can be an essential tool to meet the word-count targets of assignments, avoiding the repetition of academic long phrases. The history of abbreviations also worth a mention here, and it should be said that they are not merely linguistic, but also a historical interest. Moreover they also help to identify the cultural identity of our ancestors. For instance, one of the most popular games, nowadays, ‘GOLF’ is clarified as ‘gentlemen only ladies forbidden’. This implies at the restriction of women participation in the past, even though now women and men are equal in almost all fields. All languages contain abbreviations, abbreviations are found not only in “living languages”, but also in “dead ones”, for example, in Latin. It is interesting to note that these particular linguistic units are ones of few units which “have survived” and continue their functioning and, consequently, “live”, although in other languages, proving stability of abbreviations and their ability to function as international linguistic units.

There are two types of abbreviations that are most commonly used in academic writing: standard and non-standard abbreviations. Standard abbreviations consist of widely accepted ones like units of measurement. And this does not require the spelling out even at its first mention. On the other hand, non-standardized ones are field-

specific, and they do require the clarification of the author at the very first mention. For example, CUPA stands for Certified Unified Program Agencies.

First of all, I would like to mention some rules to use abbreviations promptly. It is recommended to abbreviate phrase, only if three or more words are included in that phrase. Applying them too much may ruin your assignment or any type of writing by making it fancy and complex to comprehend on the reader's eyes. Moreover, it is essential to define the abbreviated phrase at its first mention, unless it is defined, this may puzzle reader to flip back the pages to find the meaning of abbreviation. Because of the fact, most journals and magazines pay a special attention to use the abbreviations by setting certain ground rules to apply them in articles, they publish.

Abbreviations are actively and, perhaps, the most used in medicine. The purpose of applying them is to facilitate the communication among the doctors, along with saving space, time and effort. However, the use of abbreviations has been linked to patient safety issues. The origin of the usage of medical abbreviations can be traced back to Medieval Latin manuscripts when the limitation in writing space necessitated shortening of sentences. As Latin culture influenced medical terminology, the habit of using abbreviations became entrenched in medical culture. Conversely the widespread use of acronyms became prominent in the 20th century when such acronyms as LASER (Light Amplifications by Stimulated Emission of Radiation) and SONAR (Sound Navigation And Ranging) became popular. Moreover, abbreviations play a part in preparing patient records in a faster way. In doing so, patients can receive their treatment more quickly, this increases the potentials of the remedy.

On the other hand, there are some possible disadvantages of using abbreviations in medicine. Every so often the usage of abbreviations in clinical field may cause confusions, which is considered to be the harshest thing as the human life may happen to be at risk. According to some statistics, every year 7000 people die because of the misconceptions among doctors, and 20% of these happens due to misunderstanding abbreviations.

Furthermore, it is not uncommon to see the abbreviated name of the organizations, the most popular of them are the UNO (United Nations Organizations), WHO (World Health Organization) and more to name. The reason why the titles of organizations are often shortened is to simplify their usage in communication along with saving time and space while preparing documentations. Moreover, it is easier to make the laypeople aware of their organizational purposes in a simple form.

In linguistics, abbreviations are considered to a subject of study. A nominative function of abbreviations has recently become the most important part of linguistics, which helps to indicate new concepts and objects. In doing so, they will enrich the vocabulary of the particular language. They aid to avoid the contradictions between

needs for thinking and limited lexical sources. Also linguistics use abbreviations to title some linguistic terms, which are must learn for future pedagogues, like me. Here I would like to mention a few of them, adj means adjective, adv (adverb) people can come across these abbreviations more often in dictionaries. They are used to avoid over repetition and to save space.

Additionally, with the advancement of social media websites, texting abbreviations are getting increasingly popular day by day. Of course they are also essential to save time. However texting abbreviations are considered to be rather informal. Therefore it is recommended not to use them for formal interactions like job applications, essays and assignments. The most frequently used texting abbreviations are ASAP (as soon as possible), IDK (I don't know), IDC (I don't care), aka (also known as), btw (by the way) and more to name. These types of abbreviations are especially popular among teenagers and the youth.

In conclusion, abbreviations are widely used in different realms of human endeavor and they are much more than simply shortened form of the words. Billions of people are receiving its endless advantages by means of fast pace, saved space, minimum effort to comprehend complicated assignments.

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